

LOW TEMPERATURE HEAT CAPACITIES OF BORON FILAMENTS- AND
SILICON CARBIDE WHISKERS-REINFORCED ALUMINUM

D.P. Dandekar
Army Materials Technology Laboratory
Watertown, MA 02172
U.S.A.

and

Z.Z. Fu and J.C. Ho
Wichita State University
Wichita, KS 67208
U.S.A.

ABSTRACT

Boron-aluminum and silicon carbide-aluminum composites were evaluated calorimetrically between 2 and 7 K. In both cases the temperature dependence of heat capacity data can be fitted to $C = \gamma T + \beta T^3$. The linear term agrees well with the electronic contribution of the metal matrix. The second or lattice vibrational term yields a Debye temperature value of the composite (535 K for B-Al and 450 K for SiC-Al). This value is between those of the matrix and the filaments, and closer to that of the matrix in corroboration with earlier studies by elastic constants.

INTRODUCTION

Boron filaments- and silicon carbide whiskers-reinforced aluminum are advanced structural materials with high modulus to density ratios. The metal matrix composites, having much better electrical and thermal conductivities than those of epoxy matrix composites, are also suitable for components in electromagnetic devices. Towards cryogenic applications, only limited information are available, including one on elastic constants of boron-aluminum by Read and Ledbetter [1]. Their results suggest that the elastic constants are between the corresponding values for pure boron and aluminum, reflecting the effective bonding between the matrix and the fibers. This paper reports our low temperature calorimetric measurements on one boron-aluminum and one silicon carbide-aluminum composite. The results add to the data base for future engineering design. But more

importantly, they are analyzed in terms of the electronic and lattice heat capacities [2], based on the free electron model and the Debye model, respectively. According to these models, the low temperature heat capacity of a solid can usually be represented as

$$C = \gamma T + \beta T^3 \quad (1)$$

where the linear term is associated with conduction electrons, if any, and the T^3 term is due to lattice vibrations. The electronic heat capacity coefficient is a measure of the density of states at the Fermi level, $N(0)$:

$$\gamma = (1/3)\pi^2 k^2 N(0), \quad (2)$$

while the lattice heat capacity coefficient can be used to calculate the Debye temperature of the solid, θ_D :

$$\beta = (12\pi^4 Nk/5)(\theta_D)^{-3}, \quad (3)$$

with k being the Boltzmann constant and N the number of atoms. Eq. (1) is often rewritten as

$$C/T = \gamma + \beta T^2 \quad (4)$$

to suggest a linear relationship between C/T versus T^2 .

EXPERIMENTS AND RESULTS

The boron-aluminum (B-Al) sample has 40 vol.% B (vapor deposited over fine tungsten substrate) filaments in 6061-Al alloy. The silicon-carbide aluminum (SiC-Al) sample has 25 vol.% SiC whiskers in 2014-Al alloy. Heat capacity measurements were made between 2 and 7 K with standard adiabatic calorimetry. The sample was thermally anchored to a copper block containing a manganin wire heater and a precalibrated germanium thermometer. The heat capacity of this heater-thermometer assembly was separately measured for addenda correction. Overall uncertainty of the results was estimated to be about 2%.

The heat capacity data for B-Al is shown in Fig. 1, indeed yielding a linear fit:

$$C/T = 31.8 + 0.732 T^2. \quad (5)$$

with the heat capacity in $\mu\text{J/g-deg}$. To delineate the coefficients into meaningful terms, density and atomic mass of boron (2.35 g/cm^3 , 10.811 g/mole) and aluminum [3] (2.70 g/cm^3 , 26.98 g/mole) are first employed to convert the 40 vol.% B to 37 wt.% or 59 at.% B (ignoring the minor contribution of the tungsten substrate in boron fibers). Knowing that

$$\gamma \begin{cases} = 1,350 \mu\text{J/mole-deg}^2 & \text{for aluminum} \\ = 0 & \text{for boron,} \end{cases}$$

and

$$\beta \begin{cases} = 24 \mu\text{J/mole-deg}^4 & (\theta_D = 430 \text{ K}) & \text{for aluminum} \\ = 0.77 \mu\text{J/mole-deg}^4 & (\theta_D = 1,360 \text{ K}) & \text{for boron [4],} \end{cases}$$

a weighted average heat capacity (in $\mu\text{J/g-deg}$) for the composite can then be calculated:

$$C/T = 31.7 + 0.591 T^2, \quad (6)$$

assuming that both γ and β values are additive. The agreement between the γ values in this equation and in Eq. (5) implies that the bulk of boron filaments (apart from the very limited reaction zone at the interface) remains an insulator. On the other hand, the two β values are very different. This is what we anticipated, since the bonding at the interface couples the vibrations of the matrix and the filaments. Accordingly, the observed β is equivalent to an apparent Debye temperature of 535 K. The fact that this value is between those of boron and aluminum, and closer to that of aluminum, corroborates with the conclusion of the

Fig. 1. Heat capacity data for B-Al Composite.

earlier elastic constants work [1].

Heat capacity data for the SiC-Al sample are displayed in Fig. 2:

$$C/T = 36.8 + 0.868 T^2 \quad (7)$$

They are analyzed using the same procedure as that for boron-aluminum. First, with 2.70 g/cm^3 and 26.98 g/mole for aluminum [3] and 3.21 g/cm^3 and 40.02 g/mole for silicon carbide, the 25 vol.% SiC is converted to 28 wt.% or 21 at.% SiC. In a recent calorimetric study on pure silicon carbide, Lin, Ho, and Dandekar [5] determined for this compound:

$$\gamma = 0$$

and

$$\beta = 0.100 \text{ } \mu\text{J/g-deg}^4 \quad (\theta_D = 990 \text{ K}).$$

Consequently, the following weighted average heat capacity for the SiC-Al composite is obtained:

$$C/T = 35.8 + 0.695 T^2 \quad (8)$$

Again, γ is in reasonable agreement with the experimentally determined value in Eq. (7), whereas the two β values are significantly different.

Fig. 2. Heat capacity data for SiC-Al composite.

According to the observed β value, an apparent Debye temperature of 450 K is derived. (Note that in using Eq. (3) to calculate θ_D from β for SiC or SiC-Al, one has to carefully take into consideration the number of atoms per mole, if C is expressed as per mole. In effect, $N = nN_A$ in Eq. (3), with N_A being the Avogadro number, $n = 1$ for Al, but 2 for SiC.) This θ_D value is also between those of aluminum and silicon carbide and closer to that of aluminum.

In conclusion, this work has demonstrated that, for fiber-metal matrix composites, low temperature calorimetric measurements can be used to derive the lattice strengthening parameter -- the apparent Debye temperature, as well as the bulk change in conduction electrons, if any. For the two materials studied here, the apparent Debyetemperatures are between those of the metal matrix and the fibers, suggesting strength enhancement of the matrix. Meanwhile, the reaction zones between the matrix and fibers are very much limited as expected.

REFERENCES

1. Read, D.T. and Ledbetter, H.M., Elastic Properties of Boron-Aluminum Composites at Low Temperatures, J. Appl. Phys., 1977, 48, 2827-31.
2. See, e.g., Kittel, C., Introduction to Solid State Physics, 6th ed., John Wiley, N.Y., 1986, Chapters 5 and 6.
3. To simplify the analyses without significantly affecting the conclusions, density and atomic mass of pure aluminum are used in lieu of those of 6061- and 2014-Al alloys.
4. Gschneidner, K.A., Solid State Physics, Vol. 16, ed. F. Seitz and D. Turnbull, Academic Press, N.Y., 1964, p. 370.
5. Lin, G., Ho, J.C., and Dandekar, D.P., to be published.